

PROCEEDINGS OF THE GAMES INTERSECTIONAL SYMPOSIUM

September 19 and 20, 2025

The symposium brought together artists, researchers, designers, and community organizers working at and within the intersections of games, identity, and justice.

Organized by Games Intersectional Roundtable (GIRT).
Contact us at gamesintersectional@gmail.com.

The following contributions were presented at the first GIS 25 held online in gathertown:

Social Innovation and Video Games: Exploring Implications for Learning and Teaching

by Patrick Gregori & Milica Marković, University of Klagenfurt

Sliders for Everything (Except Gender): A Critique of Gender Norms in Video Game Character Creators through 'Your Average Character Creator'

by Eileen Carette

Disruption through Strategic Game Design: Challenging Caste Transmission Using Interactive Media

by Srikanth Sundaram

In Other Bodies - Inhabiting the Nonhuman Body in Video Games as a Means for Empathy

by Florian Schäfer

For more information, visit our [website!](https://gamesintersectional.github.io/gi-symposium25/)
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Social innovation and video games: Exploring implications for learning and teaching

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Abstract

Social innovation emerged as a solution to numerous global challenges. Education has the potential to increase awareness of these challenges and to shift mindsets towards more sustainable practices. Leveraging different methods and tools for knowledge dissemination is important to make a stronger impact. There is a growing interest in video games and their role in education. However, we lack insights concerning their application in social innovation education and teaching. Therefore, this study explores the educational video game Eco, building on autoethnographic approaches and players' online data to accommodate the experiences with the game. The findings show that the game's design facilitates different modes of learning that, in turn, enable social innovation competencies, including systems thinking, problem-solving, and communication and collaboration. The study shows that video games like Eco have the potential to be powerful tools for learning. Furthermore, it provides practical implications for implementation in teaching settings.

Keywords

Social innovation, learning, teaching, education, video games, game design